

Conference Report - Innovation and Intellectual Property Challenges in the Agri-Food Sector in the Context of Sustainable Development and European Integration

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Nadiia Stoliarchuk

Dr., National Science Center "Institute of Agrarian Economics" Kyiv (Ukraine), Intern Realization of the Program The Iwan Wyhowski Award 2023 in Faculty of Law and Administration Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań, Poland

Conference abstract

The aim of the international hybrid online conference "Challenges regarding innovation and intellectual property in the agri-food sector in the context of sustainable development and European integration" was, firstly, to present the chosen legal and economic issues concerning innovations and intellectual property in the agri-food sector; secondly, to assess how the legal regulations on the above issues respond to the problems and challenges related in the national, European and global aspect e.g. to the war in Ukraine. It is of significant importance to establish collaborations and dialogues with Researchers and Experts who are interested in innovation in the agri-food sector. 41 speakers representing academic institutions, universities, state and non-governmental organizations from Ukraine, Poland, Argentina, Belgium, Brazil, Greece, Estonia, Spain, Italy, Macedonia, Turkey took part in the conference. The issues raised in the presentations during the conference were part of a global debate on innovation and intellectual property in the agri-food sector in the EU and around the world in the context of European integration and the war in Ukraine. More than 150 people attended the conference. The variety of topical presentations confirmed the importance of innovation and intellectual property in the agricultural sector.

L'objectif de la conférence internationale hybride en ligne « Challenges regarding innovation and intellectual property in the agri-food sector in the context of sustainable development and European integration » était, premièrement, de présenter les questions juridiques et économiques choisies concernant les innovations et la propriété intellectuelle dans le secteur agroalimentaire ; deuxièmement, d'évaluer comment les réglementations juridiques sur les questions ci-dessus répondent aux problèmes et aux défis liés à l'aspect national, européen et mondial, par exemple à la guerre en Ukraine. Il est très important d'établir des collaborations et des dialogues avec des chercheurs et des experts qui s'intéressent à l'innovation dans le secteur agroalimentaire.

Das Ziel der internationalen hybriden Online-Konferenz „Challenges regarding innovation and intellectual property in the agri-food sector in the context of sustainable development and European integration“ war es, erstens die ausgewählten rechtlichen und wirtschaftlichen Fragen zu Innovationen

und geistigem Eigentum im Agrar- und Ernährungssektor darzustellen und zweitens zu bewerten, wie die rechtlichen Regelungen zu den oben genannten Themen auf die Probleme und Herausforderungen im nationalen, europäischen und globalen Zusammenhang, z.B. mit dem Krieg in der Ukraine, reagieren. Es ist von großer Bedeutung, Kooperationen und Dialoge mit Forschern und Experten aufzubauen, die an Innovationen im Agrar- und Ernährungssektor interessiert sind.

Conference Report

The international conference was held in a hybrid form, i.e. online on the MS Teams platform and at the Faculty of Law and Administration of Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznan, Poland. As many of the conference participants were from Ukraine, a country at war, the conference was mainly a virtual meeting. All sessions were conducted in English.

The conference was organized by Professor AMU Dr. hab. Aneta Suchoń (Department of Agricultural, Food and Environmental Protection Law, Faculty of Law and Administration, Poznan, Poland), and Dr. Nadiia Stoliarchuk, assistant professor, leading researcher (National Science Centre "Institute of Agrarian Economics" in Kyiv, Ukraine), with the support of the Faculty of Law and Administration of Adam Mickiewicz University.

The conference was officially opened by Prof. AMU. Dr. hab. Tomasz Nieborak, Dean of the Faculty of Law and Administration Adam Mickiewicz University, Poznań, Poland. Opening speeches were also held also by Professor María Esther Muñoz Espada, President of CEDR (European Council for Rural Law), Professor Dr. Sci. (Econ.) Yuriy Lupenko Academician of the National Academy of Sciences, Vice-President of the National Academy of Agrarian Sciences of Ukraine, Acting Director of the National Research Center "Institute of Agrarian Economics", Professor dr. hab. Roman Budzinowski, President of the Board of the Polish Association of Agricultural Lawyers, Head of the Department of Agricultural, Food and Environmental Law at Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznan.

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The conference lasted one day. It was divided into three parts - three sessions. The first of them was devoted mainly to issues of innovation in the agricultural sector and harmonization of legislation in the aspect of European integration.

The first part of the conference was opened by Mrs. Marta Iglesias, Policy Officer in Unit in DG AGRI (European Commission), Brussels, Belgium, with the presentation "European Innovation Partnership and its activities".

Prof. UAM dr. hab. Aneta Suchoń, Faculty of Law and Administration of Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań, Poland, presented her paper "Challenges regarding innovation and intellectual property in the agri-food sector - introductory remarks on theory and practice". The main objective of her presentation was to assess whether and to what extent legal regulations support innovation, including the development of intellectual property in the agri-food sector. She presented various legal issues related to innovation, especially intellectual property in agriculture, including: patents, trademarks, geographical indications and legal protection of plant varieties.

Next, Prof. María Esther Muñiz Espada, University Valladolid, Spain, introduced the topic – "Smart farming, big data and property". Dr. Nadiia Stoliarchuk, assistant professor, leading researcher at the National Scientific Centre "Institute of Agrarian Economics", Head of the Young Scientists Council, presented the topic "Legal regulation of innovative activity of Ukraine: European integration aspect". In her report, she emphasized the need for prompt and rational improvement of the technology transfer model in the agricultural sector, taking into account the European integration aspect. Prof. Dr. Sci. (Econ.) Olexandra Mandych, Finance, Banking and Insurance Department, State Biotechnological University, Kharkiv, Ukraine addressed the audience with the issue of "Digital adaptation and AI tools for Innovatization of the business financial architecture".

Then Dr. Serhieieva Natalia, Deputy Director for Scientific, Innovative and Production Activities of the Institute of Mechanics and Automatics of Agroindustrial Production of the National Academy of Agricultural Sciences of Ukraine, presented her thoughts on "Investments in the Restoration of the Ukrainian Agroindustrial Complex on an Innovative Basis in the Post-War Period". Dr. Zdnipriana-Korinna Maryana, Associate Professor, Department of Economics and Law, Educational and Scientific Institute of Economics and Management of the National University of Food Technologies, then presented the topic - "Export of agricultural products under martial law: updating legislation".

Next Prof. Dr. Giuseppe Spoto, Department of Law, Roma Tre University, Italy, presented the topic "Cultured Meat for a More Sustainable Food. Pros and cons of new technologies". Dr. Sci. (Econ.) Oleksii Kalivoshko, assoc. prof, Chief Researcher Sciences of the Department of Financial, Credit and Tax Policy, National Science Center "Institute of Agrarian Economics", Prof. of the Department of Administrative Management and Foreign Economic Activity of NUBIP of Ukraine and Mrs. Alla Myrvoda, graduate student of the Department of Financial, Credit and Tax Policy, National Science Center "Institute of Agrarian Economics", Kyiv, Ukraine addressed the audience with the issue "Innovation development in financial support for the agricultural sector amidst times of war and European integration".

Prof. Dr. Sci. (Econ.) Pavlo Muzyka, Head of the Department of Enterprise Economics, Innovations and Consulting at the AIC named after I.V. Popovich, Stepan Gzhytskyi National University of Veterinary Medicine and Biotechnologies Lviv and Dmytro Solomonko, Assistant of the Department of Enterprise Economics, Innovations and Consulting at the I.V. Popovich A.C., Stepan Gzhytskyi National University of Veterinary Medicine and Biotechnologies Lviv, discussed the topic "Innovations in the agri-food sub-complex in the context of sustainable development and food security in Europe".

Dr. Oksana Dzyundzia, Faculty of Biology and Technology, Department of Food Technologies, Kher-son State Agrarian and Economic University, Ukraine, presented her interesting paper on "Resource-saving technologies in food and processing enterprises". Dr. Bohdan Shapoval, National Science Center

"Institute of Agrarian Economics", General Manager of Ukrainian Food Association and Food Trade Support Ltd. spoke about "Marketing approaches to the distribution of Ukrainian brands in the field of food products on the international sales market". Dr. Sci. (Econ.) Studinska Galyna, Senior Research Fellow, National Scientific Centre "Institute of Agrarian Economics" presented "Brand as an innovative component of the development of agricultural enterprises".

Dr. Volodymyr Pechko, Head of the Public Union "Union of Gardeners, Vintners and Winemakers of Ukraine", Associate Professor of the Department of Processing of Agricultural Products of the National University of Food Technologies, Doctoral Candidate of the State University of Biotechnology, addressed the audience with the topic "Innovations as a component of the strategic development of the wine-growing and winemaking complex of the agricultural sector of Ukraine". Dr Agata Niewiadomska, University of Warsaw, Poland, presented an interesting report on "Smart farming as a legal challenge". Dr. Natalia Perepelitsa, Head of the Department of Scientific and Methodical Work and Training of Scientific Personnel, Institute of Mechanics and Automatics of Agroindustrial Production of the National Academy of Agricultural Sciences of Ukraine, spoke about "Innovative development of the technical and technological base of agricultural production in the context of European integration processes". Oğuzhan MANİOĞLU, PhD Researcher, John Paul II Catholic University, Lublin, Poland; Istanbul University, Social Science Institute, presented his research on "The Development of Agriculture in Turkish Culture and the Process of Integration into the European Union".

The second session dealt with issues related to the implementation of innovations, intellectual property and geographical indications. Natalia Karpenchuk-Konopatska, President of the Women's Business Chamber of Ukraine, Vice President for International Cooperation of the Lviv Chamber of Commerce and Industry, opened the second session and presented a report on "Prospects of the agricultural sector, which is the basis of the economy of Ukraine: the main challenges, risks, opportunities, innovations".

Then Sofiia Buhaienko, Intellectual Property Professional of the Ukrainian National Office for Intellectual Property and Innovation, Kyiv, Ukraine, told about "Implementation of Innovations for the Protection of Intellectual Property Rights in the Agricultural Sector". Prof. Antonios Maniatis, Lawyer at the Supreme Court of Greece, Assistant Professor of Law at the Merchant Navy Academy of Macedonia, presented "European Union Law on Geographical Indications". Dr. Inna Bezhenar, researcher at the National Scientific Centre "Institute of Agrarian Economics", Secretary of the Young Scientists Council, spoke about "Geographical indications in Ukraine: challenges and opportunities for the development of agri-food products and the creation of brands". Dr. Yuliia Kobirenko, Lviv National Environmental University, Lviv, Ukraine; Institute for Sustainable Agriculture, SCIC, Cordoba, Spain, presented her scientific results on "Restoration of degraded lands of Ukraine by applying technology of no-tillage and direct sowing of leguminous perennial grasses". Dr. Daria Yakubenko, Assistant Professor at the Constitutional Law Department of the National Law University named after Yaroslav the Wise, Ukraine, spoke on "Legislative regulation of intellectual property rights in the agro-food industry: the experience of Japan".

A very interesting and relevant presentation on "Growing Threats to Plant Breeding through Intellectual Property Laws" was given by Hajna Szücs, graduate of Tallinn University of Technology, intern

at AUDI AG, Tallinn, Estonia. Taras Griadil, Master of Medicine, Chairman of the Council of Young Scientists of SHEI "UzhNU", Assistant of the Department of Therapy and Family Medicine of the Faculty of Postgraduate Education and Pre-University Training, Assistant of the Department of Internal Medicine of the Medical Faculty №2, spoke about "Challenges related to innovation and intellectual property in the era of artificial intelligence tools".

The third session of the Conference was mainly devoted to the issues associated with food security, environmental safety and innovations in different countries of the EU and the world. Beata Magdalena Witkowska, Witkowska Law Firm, Warsaw, Poland opened third session and expressed her vision on the topic: "Food packaging like one of the key elements of EU policy towards creating a circular economy as part of the EU new Green Deal". Dr. Volodymyr Studinsky, executive director of the Scientific Research Training Center "PrintsepS" presented his speech on the topic "Economic and ecological aspects of the innovative potential of the agro-industrial complex of Ukraine in the context of the Russian-Ukrainian war". Dr. Gustavo Gonzalez Acosta, Buenos Aires University, Argentina told us about "Evaluation of environmental impact in agricultural activities in the Argentine Republic: case of the province of Buenos Aires". Igor Loureiro de Matos, Master in Law at Escola de Direito de São Paulo da Fundação Getúlio Vargas (FGV/SP), Professor at Escola Técnica Família Agrícola "A Partilha" (ETFAP), Lawyer, Board at Cooperativa de Energias Renováveis do Nordeste (Cooperne), Senior Researcher at Instituto para Cooperação e Desenvolvimento (ICADE), Brasil and Simone Pinheiro, Management Student at Universidade do Estado da Bahia (UNEB), Scholarship holder at Instituto para Cooperação e Desenvolvimento (ICADE) presented their join research on the topic "Brazilian question: agrobiodiversity and rural productivity: dilemma or complementarity".

Dr. Hanna Tiutiunnyk, Researcher, Scientific secretary of the Department of Economic&Ecological Seaside Regions Development, First Deputy Head of the Council of Young Scientists of SO "IMEER NAS of Ukraine", associate member of the Council of Young Scientists at the Odesa Regional State Administration presented a report on the topic "Aquaculture Innovations: Addressing Environmental Challenges Stemming from Military Actions towards Sustainable Development of Water Resources". Dr. Tetiana Lutska, associate prof. at the Economics and Law Department, National University of Food Technologies, Kyiv, Ukraine expressed her vision on the topic "Effects of organic farming in the UK and Ukraine".

At the end of the conference, three papers were presented by young scientists from the Adam Mickiewicz University of Poznan. Mgr. Zuzanna Rura, Master in Law, Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań, Poland with presentation "Selected legal aspects of organic farming in Poland and Tunisia – innovation and tradition". Mgr. Magdalena Jeziernicka, Ph.D. Candidate, Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań, Poland with speech "Eco schemes as part of sustainable development of agriculture". And Mgr. Tomasz Marzec, Ph.D. Candidate, Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań, Poland with presentation "Community energy: the challenges of ensuring a fair and innovative energy transition in Europe". The concluding remarks of the Conference were presented by Professor AMU Dr. hab. Aneta Suchoń.

In conclusion – 41 speakers representing academic institutions, universities, state and non-governmental organizations from Ukraine, Poland, Argentina, Belgium, Brazil, Greece, Estonia, Spain, Italy, Macedonia, Turkey took part in the conference. The issues raised in the presentations during the conference were part of a global debate on innovation and intellectual property in the agri-food sector in the EU and around the world in the context of European integration and the war in Ukraine. The variety of topical speeches confirmed the importance of innovation and intellectual property in the agricultural sector. More than 150 people attended the conference. The variety of topical presentations confirmed the importance of innovation and intellectual property in the agricultural sector.